

EFFECTS OF ETHICAL LEADERSHIP AND ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE ON EMPLOYEE JOB INVOLVEMENT

Isaac Boakyeⁱ

University of Applied Management,
Ghana Campus, Ghana

Abstract:

Employee outcomes have been described to be a nexus of several factors. The study sought to as ethical leadership and organizational involvement as possible antecedents of employee job involvement. The study also enquired about the job involvement level of managers and non-managers. Various banks in Ghana were selected for the study. The study comprised of 192 respondents who were mainly leaders and subordinates from selected banks who were selected using the purposive sampling and simple random sampling technique respectively. Data collected from the field was analyzed using regression and independent ample t-test. The findings of the study indicated that there was a positive relationship between ethical leadership and employee job involvement. Furthermore, the study revealed a positive relationship between organizational climate and employee job involvement. Ethical leadership proved to be a more significant antecedent to employee job involvement than organizational climate. Furthermore, the study also found that there was no significant difference in employee job involvement due to respondents' position as manager or non-manager. It was recommended that leaders should take into consideration their behaviors within the organization as these go a long way to affect employee behavior. Further, firms can develop thinking walls where quotes about ethical leader behavior which impacts organizational climate will be announced. Limitations as well as area for further study have been discussed.

Keywords: organizational climate, ethical leadership, employee job involvement

ⁱ Correspondence: email isaacboakyeyeboah@gmail.com

1. Introduction

Human Psychologists have asserted that the behavior of individuals is a nexus of several factors within the environment the person finds himself in. These factors affect the overall wellbeing of the individual which is then translated into the way they handle other aspects of their lives (Bodner, 2011). What this implies is that the overall wellbeing of an individual can have an adverse effect on their behaviors. This is because humans have been identified as reflective of the climate in which they find themselves; hence, for most of the times, they will exhibit the elements that surround them. The implication to organizations is that, in order to ensure positive responses from their workers, it is prudent that they pay attention to several factors that affect the behavior of employees. Leadership plays a huge role in helping organizations to meet their goals. The behavior of leaders at various levels of an organization affects the conduct of subordinates which is then translated into the achievement of positive or negative outcomes both in the long and short run life cycle of an organization. Hence, the behavior of leaders has attracted the interest of management researchers (Bowden, 2003).

Leaders, by virtue of their status and position, have some form of power that is formally recognized, however, the negative use of this power can have rippling negative effect on the organization or nation at large. The way leaders tend to express this power is what affects the overall perception employees have about the organization which is then translated into how they go about what they do and their ability to involve themselves in the various activities of the firm. What this implies is that, the climate one finds himself in shapes him or her and has a great tendency of revealing or diminishing the potentials of an individual. In the work setting, the implication for management is that the choice of leaders is very important first because they carry with them a form of organizational climate which can greatly affect the level of job involvement of subordinates (Coyne, 2011). Glick (2012) expressed that job involvement has been misinterpreted as the level to which employees contribute to work processes within organizations, he therefor opined that job involvement goes beyond the tradition of what the employee does to what he would want to do had all other factors that will make his work easier to perform been present. Drawing from this explanation, employee job involvement is very crucial to firms and may be very difficult to measure the concept.

Northouse (2010) confirms that leaders have an enormous role to play when it comes to organizational climate. After reviewing several leadership theories, he concluded that change is constantly occurring in today's world. Both innovation and leadership require deliberate actions that can help or hinder an organization's ability to

effectively deal with (Brown, Treviño, & Harrison, 2005). The word action may be seen as what a person does after deliberately choosing between different alternatives; but behavior is an empirically observable response to stimuli (Caldwell, Hayes, & Long, 2010). Perceptions about patterns of behavior tend to represent much of the research on organizations, even though leadership, organizational culture and climate tend to be entwined (Coyne, 2011). The study was based on the social learning theory by Bandura (1966). The theory posits that the outcomes of employees is as a result of the interactions they have with their superiors. Put differently, employee outcome is a nexus of several factors within the organization, as a result, those factors when monitored can bring about positive outcomes, in this study, organizational climate and ethical leadership are two very broad and important factors that shape the daily operations of a firm and hence affects output (Alhawary, & Aborumman, 2011). The study therefore seeks to ascertain whether the claims of the social learning theory are applicable to situations where there is high or low impact of organizational climate and ethical leadership behavior.

To a large extent, a climate that encourages creativity and innovation can be seen as an outcome of individual leadership style (Elizur & Koslowsky, 2000) Leaders within organizations have social power and can influence and motivate followers toward certain actions (Harash, 2010). Rather than focusing entirely on the motivational aspects or the intentions behind certain actions ethical leaders, Brown, Trevino and Harrison (2005) emphasized the behavioral aspects of ethical leadership (Glick, 2012). In organizations, effective leadership is not one sided; like ethics, leadership requires a symbiotic relationship with others. For example, the behaviors that ethical leaders exhibit have been shown to have positive relationships with follower trust and perceived organizational effectiveness (Johnson, 2007).

Leadership and change have been popular topics for research, but there is a lack of research of the ethical aspects between the two (Bowen, Kurzweil, & Tobin, 2005). All organizations must deal with change; effective leadership and a climate that is supportive of innovation are critical components in determining whether change efforts will be seen as appropriate (Samad, 2005). Research has shown that there is a relationship between transformational leadership, which includes an ethical component (Brown et al., 2005) and an organizational climate of innovation (Robbins, & Judge, 2008) This study extends research on ethical leadership by determining whether there is also a relationship between it and a climate for innovation.

1.2 Problem Statement

Due to today's rapidly changing environment, organizations must continually innovate or the likelihood is that their survival will be short-lived (Euban, 2013). Among the

myriad of challenges that organizations face, one of their greatest challenges is establishing a climate where innovation thrives. An innovative climate is important because it is part of creating and sustaining an organization's competitive advantage. There are many vital aspects that help organizations be more innovative, including their organizational structure and use of technology. However, organizational leadership is the most important element (Abgor, 2008). Leaders are the catalyst for successful innovation because for innovation to *"bring any real benefit, the leadership must support, sustain, encourage, and inspire followers to make it work"* (Abgor, 2008, p. 40). Effective leaders encourage followers to ask questions about why things are done certain ways and to look for new ways to streamline or eliminate unnecessary steps in a process. Employees' willingness to suggest ideas for improvements or experiment with new processes requires a trusting relationship between leaders and followers because risks of failure exist when people try out new ideas. In order, therefore, for organizations to have innovation and creativity that produces positive and sustainable results, leaders must exhibit a style of leadership that encourages the means and ends to be consistent with these. There have been studies that explored the relationship between the transformational style of leadership and organizational innovation. For example, Cullen, Parboteeah, and Victor (2012) found a relationship between transformational leadership and the promotion of technological innovation. In another study, the causal relationship between leaders' transformational leadership behaviors and their business units' one-year performance was moderated by the units' level of support for innovation (Meyer and Allen, 2004)). Organizational culture was also found to be a mediator between transformational leadership and an organization's climate for innovation (Saari, & Judge, 2004). This study seeks to contribute to the ongoing discussion by further assessing the relationship between ethical leadership, organizational climate and employee job involvement while ascertaining the role of demographic variables in leader's ethical behavior.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The overall objective of the study will be to examine the influence of ethical leadership on organizational climate. To achieve this goal, the specific objectives will be to:

1. To determine the relationship between ethical leadership and employee job involvement.
2. To identify the relationship between organizational climate and employee job involvement.
3. To ascertain whether organizational climate has more variance on ethical leadership than employee job involvement.

4. To identify the relationship between employee status and employee job involvement.
5. To ascertain the relationship between employee area of operation and employee job involvement.

1.4 Research Hypothesis

The following research hypothesis will guide the study:

H1a: There is a relationship between ethical leadership and employee job involvement.

H2a: There is a relationship between organizational climate and employee job involvement.

H3a: Organizational climate will have more on ethical leadership than employee job involvement.

H4a: There is a relationship between employee status and employee job involvement.

H5a: There is a relationship between employee area of operation and employee job involvement.

2. Methodology

Creswell (2005) explained that in order to select a particular research design for a study, it is very critical to assess the objectives formulated for the study. Based on this premise, the study employed the descriptive form of research design to provide solutions to the research problems. Furthermore, the study adopted a correlational design to ascertain the effect of ethical leadership and organizational climate on employee job involvement. The primary objective of this study is to ascertain the relationship between ethical leadership, organizational culture and employee job involvement. In view of this, a quantitative approach was chosen for the study. The purpose for the choice of this approach is due to the fact that the study quantified variables such as ethical leadership, organizational climate and employee job involvement. According to Creswell (2005), quantitative approach is described by the use of statistical analysis to describe, and establish the relationship between the dependent and independent variable.

2.1 Population and Sampling

The target population for the current study comprises all the leaders and subordinates of the financial institutions in Accra. The study adopted a two stage random sampling technique in selecting the leaders as well as the subordinates of the various microfinance firms that were considered for the study. First of all, the study employed a

simple random sampling technique in selecting the firms. That is, every financial institution in Accra had an equal chance of being selected. However, the study ensured that financial institution that have been in existence for more than ten (10) years were selected since it was prudent for conducting a study that was relationship bias (Brackner, (1992). Out of the financial institution that was selected, the purposive sampling technique was used to select the leaders within each firm. Subordinates on the other hand were selected using the simple random technique to allow for an equal chance of being selected for every subordinate. The sample for the study was made up of three hundred participants. More specifically, 50 microfinance firms in Accra were selected. Out of the 50 firms that was selected, the three topmost leaders for each firm based on their organizational hierarchy and order of reporting. This implied that in all, 150 leaders were selected. Furthermore, three subordinates were also selected from each firm to match the number of leaders chosen from every firm. That is, a total of 150 subordinates were also chosen. The total number of sample size for this study was therefore 300. The sample size was based on the recommendations of Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) which specifies that for an appropriate sample size for studies involving the use of multiple regression, the sample size (N) should be $(N > 50 + 8M)$ where "M" is the total number of independent variables. Since there is only two (2) independent variables in the study, the minimum sample size required for this study was sixty-six (66) [i.e., $50 + 8(2) = 66$]. Therefore, the sample size of 300 respondents more than satisfies the recommended sample size for the purpose of the present study.

2.2 Instrumentation for Study Variables

The ethical leadership behavior of leaders was measured using the ethical leadership scale developed by Brown et al. (2005). Individual subordinates were asked to rate the ethical leadership behavior of supervisors. It is a ten itemized scale with sample items such as "My leader listens to what employees have to say", "My leader disciplines employees who violate ethical standards" and "My leader conducts his/her personal life in an ethical manner". Responses are arranged on a five point Likert scale of 1 to 5 as follows *Strongly Disagree = 1, Disagree = 2, Neutral = 3, Agree = 4, Strongly Agree = 5*. Scores on the scale range from 10 to 50 with higher scores indicating that the leader is more ethical. For the purposes of this study setting, to prevent ambiguity, the scale was adapted. For instance, "My leader disciplines employees who violate ethical standards" was changed into "My headmaster disciplines employees who violate ethical standards". That is for all items on the scale, "My leader" was replaced with "My headmaster" or "My assistant headmaster" where necessary. A study by Walumbwa and Schaubroeck (2009) sought to establish a relationship between the big five personality trait and ethical leadership reported a reliability of .90. A similar study by Kalshoven 2010 reported an internal reliability of

.86. Furthermore, employee job involvement was measured using Edward's Job Involvement Questionnaire (1984) include 20 items and are based on a scale of 4 degrees from agree to strongly disagree. On the other hand, DeCottis and Koys (1991) organizational climate questionnaires were used to measure organizational climate.

2.3 Preliminary Analysis

Before the analysis of the data, the researcher conducted some preliminaries to conclude whether the data met some assumptions with regards to correlation and regression analysis which were the main statistical analysis adopted in the study. A cursory observation was done to check the data for errors and inconsistency as well as outliers. The analysis revealed that there were no significant outliers. However, issues of missing data were found and were replaced using the mean of the data for that section. According to Field (2005), for a regression analysis, the skewness and kurtosis value should be within the range -1 and +1. From the table below it can be observed that normality assumptions was not violated and hence the data was ready for further analysis.

Table 4.1: Normality Test and Descriptive Statistics of Study Variables (N=192)

Variables	Kurtosis	Skew-ness	Cronbach's Alpha	Mean	S.D
Organizational Climate	-.529	.229	.630	4.12	1.212
Employee Job Involvement	.242	-.150	.910	8.22	1.025

2.4 Multicollinearity Testing of Study Variables

It is very important to test whether some of the predicting variables are highly correlated with the other or not. In order to prove this assertion, Multicollinearity testing of variables is important (Reyes, 2013). It has been proposed that this analysis can be done using the correlation matrix, however the researcher determined to employ a more rigorous statistical analysis, hence the regression output. According to De Vaus (2002), a variance inflation factor should not exceed 10 while the tolerance value should also not exceed 10. From the table below, it can be concluded that the study variable did not violate the multicollinearity assumption.

Table 4.2: Multicollinearity Test of Independents Variables - Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	1.621	.495		3.274	.001		
ELS	.174	.082	.172	2.122	.036	.981	1.019
OCS	-.016	.373	-.004	-.044	.965	.977	1.023

a. Dependent Variables: Ethical Leadership and Organizational Climate

2.5 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Out of the 192 respondents sampled for the study, 156 were males while the remaining 36 were females. Furthermore, 101 of the total respondents had attained a minimum of first degree certificate. Thus this was necessary for the quality of data to be collected from respondents. A majority of the respondents were also within the ages of 36 to 50 years. Furthermore, the data was collected from 96 managers as well as non-managers.

A. Effect of Organizational climate on employee job involvement

To ascertain the effect of organizational climate on the job involvement of employees, a regression analysis was employed. The results of the analysis have been tabulated below:

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.325 ^a	.226	.101	3.49246

a. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational Climate

A look at the table above is indicative of the fact that, the organizational climate of selected firms causes a 22.6% variance in employee job involvement.

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	13.953	1.226	11.383	.000
	Org. Climate	.333	.071	.325	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Involvement

The regression output displayed above establishes the relationship as well as the effect of organizational climate on employee job involvement. According to the table above,

organizational climate has a significant positive relationship ($\beta=0.325$, $p<0.05$) with employee job involvement. Furthermore, employee job involvement in terms of organizational climate can be expressed as $13.953 + 0.333$ (organizational climate). Thus, at any point there is a positive increase in organizational climate, there will also be a 0.333 increment in employee job involvement.

B. Job involvement between managers and non-managers

In order to achieve this, an independent sample t-test was employed where manager and non-managers were entered into the model as the two grouped been monitored. The results of the analysis have been displayed below:

Group Statistics

	Gender of leaders	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Job Involvement	Managers	96	6.7788	.88596	.14187
	Non-Managers	96	7.0238	.81645	.17816

*p is not significant @ .05 level of significance

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means			
		F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Job Involvement	Equal variances assumed	.370	.545	-1.049	190	.298	-.24496
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.076	187.76	.288	-.24496

From the output table above it can be inferred that there is no statistically significant difference in the job involvement behavior ($t_{(190)} = -1.049$, $p>.05$) of managers ($M= 6.78$, $SD= 0.89$) and non-managers ($M= 7.02$, $SD= 0.82$). That is, there is enough statistical evidence to conclude that the hypothesis four is invalid. Hence, hypothesis four was supported.

C. Effect of Years of service on extent of job involvement

In order to achieve this aim, a regression analysis was computed where years of service was entered as the independent variable and job involvement was entered as the dependent variable. The results of the analysis have been displayed below:

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.125 ^a	.112	.211	2.24152

a. Predictors: (Constant), Org.Climate

A look at the table above is indicative of the fact that, years of experience of an employee at the workplace of selected firms causes a 11.2% variance in employee job involvement.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	15.242	2.013		8.249	.000
	Years of Exp.	.412	.170	.125	1.964	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Involvement

The regression output displayed above establishes the relationship as well as the effect of years of experience on employee job involvement. According to the table above, years of experience has a significant weak positive relationship ($\beta=0.125$, $p<0.05$) with employee job involvement. Furthermore, employee job involvement in terms of years of experience can be expressed as $15.242 + 0.412$ (years of experience). Thus, at any point there is a positive increase in organizational climate, there will also be a 0.412 increment in employee job involvement.

3. Discussion of Results**3.1 The effect of organizational climate on employee job involvement**

The study hypothesized that there will be a positive effect of organizational climate on employee job involvement. This was supported in the study analysis. Organizational climate is necessary to predict employee behavior such as job involvement in the sense that the organizational climate one finds himself in is critical to determine the behavior the person puts up. This is also buttressed by the social learning theory which posits that employee behavior is an exchange of several factors that surrounds the employee (Srivastava, 2014). Dimotakis, Scott and Koopman (2010) for instance revealed in their study that the atmosphere that persists in a workplace to a large extent determines the metal attitude of employees and enables them to either engage in creative thinking,

increased organizational citizenship behavior or not. Furthermore, Mogaji (1997) conducted a study that sought to establish the relationship between organizational climate and employee job involvement. The outcomes demonstrated that structure and obligation had fundamentally positive relationship with employee job involvement. On time remuneration had a positive however insignificant connection with employee job involvement. Organizational climate is built either consciously or unconsciously by the behavior of management, this is noticed by employees and employee modify their behaviors to suit the climate they find themselves in. What this implies is that management in some cases may not be aware of such behaviors and their consequences, hence being self-aware is critical to leadership and management.

3.2 Manager and Non-Managers' attitude towards Job Involvement

Some commentators have defined job involvement to the extent of the level to which an employee is occupied with his or her daily work. The level of job engagement can be dictated by a man's needs, values, hardworking attitude (individual qualities), condition and the position one plays in the organization. Look into has demonstrated that there is a connection between occupation inclusion the position one plays inside an association. While senior supervisors are relied upon to show most extreme responsibility since they are required to be responsible for everything, non-managers do not really consider themselves to be the primary players inside the association and subsequently they have a tendency to unwind when hard times arise and abandon them in the hands of administrators (PSUWC, 2010). To some degree, some have likewise contended that non-managers can without much of a stretch have a negative feeling towards work and the association all in all. Along these lines, people who hold a contrary state of mind towards their work may likewise encounter bring down occupation fulfilment. The joined impact of negative state of mind toward one's work and low occupation fulfilment can bring about expanded non-appearance and turnover, as the individuals who are not completely occupied with their employments will probably be truant from work or to leave the association. Keeping representatives drew in is one of the greatest difficulties for administrators. Upbeat individuals are ordinarily beneficial individuals, and research recommends connections are the greatest single determinant of efficiency inside a gathering (Stirling, 2008). The objective is to motivate representatives to relate to and think about their occupations. The more noteworthy the accomplishment at this, the more the occupation ends up plainly essential to every representative's mental self-portrait, or work personality, which mirrors the fundamental meaning of employment inclusion (Judge, 2007).

3.3 Years of Experience and Job Involvement

As indicated by vocation improvement models (Peterson, 2002) the advancement and support of occupation contribution will contrast crosswise over profession stages, along these lines, one's time of understanding at work as spoke to by age. In the early vocation arrange, level of contribution will differ in view of an individual's chances and the accessibility of appealing choices (Peterson, 2002). Those in the early vocation arrange confront the conflicting errands of making responsibilities and keeping choices open. A person in the early profession organize endeavours to wind up plainly settled in an occupation that interests her or him, yet in the event that this employment demonstrates improper, she or he doesn't dither to pick another. Representatives at this stage express more prominent expectation to leave their association and more ability to migrate than those in other age bunches (Randolph, & Johnson, 2005). In light of this, times of experience is relied upon to be a vital determinant of occupation contribution in the early profession arrange. The encounters and chances of workers at this stage will fluctuate essentially and will bring about various occupation inclusion levels relying upon the quantity of option business openings. Such varieties, spoke to by the worker's years of experience, will strongly affect work contribution of representatives at this stage. Individuals in the midcareer stage are more inspired by creating stable work and individual lives and in making solid duties to work, family, and the group. Individuals in the late phase of their vocation are in a phase of relative quietness. They are more situated to "settling down" and are less ready to move or leave the association for reasons for advancement. Mowday (2013) contended that levels of responsibility created amid the early business time frame seem to stay stable. Additionally, expanded interests as time and vitality make it progressively troublesome for representatives to leave their employments wilfully. The relative strength of responsibility levels alongside expanded challenges in leaving the association debilitate the connection between years of experience and years of involvement in the mid and late profession stages. Along these lines, one would anticipate a weaker connection between years of experience and occupation inclusion in the mid and late vocation stages than in the early profession organize on the grounds that almost no variety in levels of employment association are normal in the later profession stages.

3.4 Conclusions

Some constructive conclusions can be deduced based on the findings of the study. That is, it can be concluded that ethical leadership plays a very critical role in the work related outcomes of employees within an organization. That is, the ethical behavior of leaders impact on the job involvement of employees. The implication for practical research is that organizations should not take for granted ethical principles and

practices within organizations. Furthermore, the climate that is built or perceived within an organization determines the degree to which employees get actively involved in the operations of the organizations. Thus, employee job involvement is a nexus of several organizational factors such as ethical leadership and organizational climate. Besides, studies have revealed that managers and non-managers have a different perspective towards commitment on the job. That is, managers are tasked with accountability and are supposed to explain for any short falls within the organization, hence they tend to be more job involved than on-managers, however, some researchers have observed that the job involvement of individuals within an organization could be explained from several perspectives and due to several factors. Based on the findings of the study, there was no significant difference in job involvement due to manager or non-manager status.

3.5 Recommendations

According to the obtained results, the following recommendations are offered:

Since there is no significant relationship between the ethical behavior of managers and job involvement of employees in organizations, it is recommended that in order to increase job involvement, ethical behavior of managers and employees in organizations be enhanced. Also, it must be trained to them. Managers and employees may be trained to identify ethical issues and behaviors through workshops. In addition, through assessing the ethical behavior of managers by surveying the employees, managers who follow the ethical principles should be encouraged. Given the relationship between job involvement and organizational commitment, it is necessary to consider the assignment of responsibilities and duties according to the capability, experience and education and changing the employment status from contract to official and contractual position by managers so that hereby, job involvement is enhanced and finally, the more commitment of employees to the organization be provided.

Rosser, Johnsrud and Heck (2003) found that leaders play a vital role in the growth of organizations, competing with other institutions, and meeting shareholders expectations. Most critically, however, it should not be overlooked as to the role these leaders play establishing the culture and climate, most specifically the ethical climate at institutions. Decision making processes, creations of values, establishment of organizational norms, modes and methods of communication, perceptions of fairness, trust, honesty, are all significant contributors to perceived ethical climate that are in the control of the administrators.

It is the leader's responsibility to model the ethical behavior that he or she wants from followers. The findings from the present research imply that when subordinates perceive their organization's climate to be egoistic they will subsequently report lower

levels of commitment and satisfaction. Lower levels of employee involvement and satisfaction are linked to higher levels of absenteeism and turnover, increased withdrawal behaviors and negative attitudes, as well as lower levels of productivity and creativity. If administrators want to boost the job satisfaction and involvement levels of their faculty members, it is imperative that educational leaders behave in manners that encourage an organizational climate of benevolence. Creating an open process of communication and shared governance is one matter that could increase the perception of a benevolent ethical climate. Administrators may find that by establishing an ethical climate based upon benevolent principles may in turn produce positive operational outcomes.

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